

Formation of 3-Amino-1,5,6,7-tetrahydro-4*H*-indol-4-ones from 2-(2-Oxo-2-arylethyl)-1,3-cyclohexanediones and *N,N*-Disubstituted-hydrazines†

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Phenacyldimedones (1a–d) undergo an anomalous reaction with *N,N*-disubstituted-hydrazines to afford 3-amino-1,5,6,7-tetrahydro-4*H*-indol-4-ones (3), with only 1d, additionally yielding the 'normal' product 2a. A mechanism is postulated for the novel reaction of 1a with *N,N*-dimethylhydrazine involving species 16 and 17 as intermediates. This is substantiated by reaction of 1a with *N,N*-dimethylhydrazine and excess of other amines like morpholine, *N,N*-dibenzylamine, aniline and *n*-propylamine leading to products 3d, 3f, 3j and 4 respectively. 3f is hydrogenolysed to 3i and thence deaminated to known 2-phenyltetrahydroindole (9a). Reaction of aminocyclohexenone (10) with phenylglyoxal and morpholine affords 3d. *N*-Aminopiperidine reacts with the acyclic triketone (7) to afford only the 'normal' product 8, while with 18, ketotetrahydroindoles 9b and 23 are formed through a complex sequence of reactions.

SOME years ago, we reported that while 2-phenacyldimedone (1a) and analogues underwent reaction with hydrazine and monosubstituted hydrazines to form 5-keto-1,4,5,6,7,8-hexahydrocinnolines^{1,2}, their behaviour towards a few *N,N*-disubstituted-hydrazines was anomalous. The products were not the expected 1-substituted-perhydroindoles (2), and were identified as 3-amino-1,5,6,7-tetrahydro-4*H*-indol-4-ones (3). Structures 3 were based on analytical and spectroscopic data, deamination of 3i to the known ketotetrahydroindole (9a) and synthesis of 3d from aminoketone (10), phenyl glyoxal and morpholine. We have subsequently explored the scope of this novel reaction with a variety of *N,N*-disubstituted-hydrazines and ketones 1a–e and 7. We have also gained insight into the possible course of the reaction which in turn allowed us to devise an interesting modification to yield further examples of 3. We present in this paper full details of our studies.

- (1a) R = Ph, R₁ = Me
 (1b) R = 4-Br C₆H₄, R₁ = Me
 (1c) R = 4-F C₆H₄, R₁ = Me
 (1d) R = Ph, R₁ = H
 (1e) R = Me
- (2a) R = Ph, R₁ = H
 >N = 1-piperidinyl

Phenacyldimedone (1a) and six *N,N*-disubstituted-hydrazines afforded the ketotetrahydroindoles (3a–f; Table 1). Yields were in the range 43–66% without any effort at optimisation. Mother liquors from larger runs of the reaction between 1a and *N,N*-dimethylhydrazine were carefully investigated for material balance. Chromatography gave small amounts of methylene-bis-dimedone (5) and a coloured product, C₂₀H₂₈N₂O₂, considered tentatively to be 6 on the basis of ir and nmr data. The reaction of 4-bromophenyl (1b) and 4-fluorophenyl (1c) ketones respectively with *N*-aminomorpholine and *N*-aminopiperidine was facile yielding 3g (60%) and 3h (55%). In contrast, in one study with 2-phenacylcyclohexane-1,3-dione (1d) and *N*-aminopiperidine, the 'anomalous' product 3k was obtained only in 17% yield, while the 'normal' product 2a was formed to the extent of 31%. From the reaction of acetyl dimedone (1e) and *N,N*-dimethylhydrazine, only small amounts of 5 could be obtained. The origin of 5 in reactions involving *N,N*-dimethyl-

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TABLE 1—PHYSICAL, AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS (3)[†]

Compd. no.	R	R ₁	N<	Yield* %	M.p.** °C	Mol. formula (Mol. weight)	ν _{max} (nujol) cm ⁻¹	δ [†]
3a	H	Me	NMe ₂	66 ^a	250–52 ^c	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ N ₂ O (282.4)	3 210, 1 600	^m 1.07 (6H, s, 2OH ₂), 2.27 (2H, s, C–5H ₂), 2.67 (8H, s, C–7H ₂ , 2NCH ₃), 7.10–7.60 (m, 3ArH), 7.6–7.80 (m, 2ArH), 11.20 (br s, NH)
3b	H	Me	1-Piperidinyl	51 ^a	273–75 ^d	C ₂₁ H ₂₆ N ₂ O (322.4)	3 160, 1 630	^m 1.07 (6H, s, 2OH ₂), 1.30–1.70 (6H, m, CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂), 2.28 (2H, s, C–5H ₂), 2.65 (2H, s, C–7H ₂), 2.80–3.10 (4H, m, CH ₂ NCH ₂), 6.90–7.50 (m, 3ArH), 7.45–7.95 (m, 2ArH), 11.17 (br s, NH)
3c	H	Me	1-Hexahydroazepinyl	48 ^a	249–50 ^e	C ₂₃ H ₂₈ N ₂ O (336.5)	3 200, 1 610	^m +1.07 (6H, s, 2OH ₂), 1.70–1.90 (8H, m, (CH ₂) ₄), 2.28 (2H, s, C–5H ₂), 2.67 (2H, s, C–7H ₂), 2.95–3.30 (4H, m, CH ₂ NCH ₂), 7.00–7.60 (m, 3ArH), 7.90–8.15 (m, 2ArH), 10.70 (br s, NH)
3d	H	Me	4-Morpholinyl	53 ^a 55 ^b	297–98 ^f	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₂ (324.4)	3 160, 1 610	^m +1.07 (6H, s, 2OH ₂), 2.27 (2H, s, C–5H ₂), 2.68 (2H, s, C–7H ₂), 3.00 (4H, m, CH ₂ –NCH ₂), 3.65 (4H, m, CH ₂ OCH ₂), 7.00–7.60 (m, 3ArH), 7.80–8.10 (m, 2ArH), 11.33 (br s, NH)
3e	H	Me	1-Methyl-4-piperazinyl	65 ^a	272–74 ^g	C ₂₁ H ₂₇ N ₂ O ₂ (337.5)	3 160, 1 630	^m 1.03 (6H, s, 2OH ₂), 2.17 (3H, s, NCH ₃), 2.20 (2H, s, C–5H ₂), 2.23–2.40 (4H, m, CH ₂ –NCH ₂), 2.70 (2H, s, C–7H ₂), 6.95–7.48 (m, 3ArH), 7.50–7.90 (m, 2ArH), 11.15 (br s, NH)
3f	H	Me	N(OH ₂ C ₆ H ₄) ₂	43 ^a 12 ^b	203–05 ^h (Chloroform–hexane)	C ₂₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ O (284.6)	3 220, 1 620	^m 1.05 (6H, s, 2OH ₂), 2.30 (2H, s, C–5H ₂), 2.62 (2H, s, C–7H ₂), 4.22 (4H, s, 2ArOH), 6.90–7.50 (m, 5ArH), 7.10 (10H, s, 2 C ₆ H ₄ OH ₂), 9.00 (br s, NH)
3g	4-Br	Me	4-Morpholinyl	60 ^a	>300 ⁱ	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ BrN ₂ O ₂ (403.3)	3 140, 1 610	^m 1.08 (6H, s, 2OH ₂), 2.28 (2H, s, C–5H ₂), 2.70 (2H, s, C–7H ₂), 3.00 (4H, m, CH ₂ NH ₂), 3.70 (4H, m, CH ₂ OCH ₂), 7.55 (m, 2ArH), 7.90 (m, 2ArH), 11.40 (br s, NH)
3h	4-F	Me	1-Piperidinyl	55 ^a	287–88 ^j (Ethanol–methanol)	C ₂₁ H ₂₅ FN ₂ O (340.4)	3 160, 1 610	^m 1.05 (6H, s, 2OH ₂), 1.30–1.80 (6H, m, CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂), 2.20 (2H, s, C–5H ₂), 2.63 (2H, s, C–7H ₂), 2.75–3.15 (m, 4H, CH ₂ NCH ₂), 7.10 (m, 2ArH), 7.37 (m, 2ArH), 11.17 (br s, NH)
3i	H	Me	NH ₂	50	221–23 ^d	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ N ₂ O (254.3)	3 440, 3 330, 3 240, 1 620	^m 1.08 (6H, s, 2OH ₂), 2.18 (2H, s, C–5H ₂), 2.60 (2H, s, C–7H ₂), 4.80 (br s, NH ₂), 6.80–7.60 (m, 5 ArH), 10.92 (br s, NH)
3j	H	Me	NHC ₆ H ₅	6 ^b	270–72 ^d	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ O (330.4)	3 380, 3 200, 1 610	^m 1.07 (6H, s, 2OH ₂), 2.17 (2H, s, C–5H ₂), 2.68 (2H, s, C–7H ₂), 6.30–7.70 (m, 10 ArH), 6.65 (br s, ArNH), 11.22 (br s, pyrrole NH)
3k	H	H	1-Piperidinyl	17 ^a	207–09 ^k	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ N ₂ O (294.4)	3 220, 1 610	^m 1.20–1.80 (6H, m, CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂), 2.08 (2H, q, C–6H ₂), 2.45 (2H, t, C–5H ₂), 2.80 (2H, t, C–7H ₂), 2.85–3.20 (4H, m, CH ₂ NCH ₂), 7.00–7.60 (m, 3ArH), 7.60–8.00 (m, 2ArH), 9.00 (br s, NH)

[†]All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

^aMethod-A; ^bMethod-B; ^{**}Solvent for crystallisation: ^cAcetone–EtOH, ^dEtOH, ^eCHCl₃–EtOH, ^fTHF–EtOH, ^gaq EtOH, ^hCHCl₃–hexane, ⁱacetone, ^jEtOH–MeOH, ^kMeOH, ^lacetone–MeOH.

[†]In ^mDMSO-d₆, ⁿCDCl₃, ^oCCl₄.

hydrazine is not easily understood. Lastly, the acyclic triketone, phenacyl acetylaceton (7) and *N*-aminopiperidine gave a poor yield of 1-piperidinopyrrole (8). 1-Unsubstituted-3-aminotetrahydroindoles of this study were characterised by the presence in the ir spectrum of a very broad NH band around 3 100–3 200 cm^{-1} and C=O band between 1 610 and 1 630 cm^{-1} , and a broad singlet signal due to NH in the ^1H nmr spectrum at around δ 11.2 ppm which disappeared with D_2O . 1-Amino compounds 2a and 8 on the other hand were readily identified by the presence in their ^1H nmr spectra of a singlet due to the proton on the β -carbon atom at δ 6.30 and 5.83 ppm respectively.

Structures 3 were proved in two ways. Dibenzyl-amino derivative 3f was hydrogenolysed to the 3-aminoindole (3i) which was deaminated to the known 2-phenyltetrahydroindole (9a)². Secondly, aminoketone (10) was allowed to react with phenyl glyoxal and morpholine to afford 3d although only in 6% yield.

In contrast to the phenacyldimedone (1a), 2-phenacylcyclohexanone (11) and *N*-aminopiperidine afforded only the 1-piperidino derivative (12) and not the 3-piperidinoindole (13)². Taking this fact into account, we visualise the formation of 3a from 1 (Chart 1) to occur through the enaminone (14) wherein the hydrazine *N,N*-bond is weakened to facilitate an intramolecular transfer of the disubstituted amino group as shown to form 15. The latter can lead to the formation of 3a via 16, which

Chart 1

in turn will be in a reversible equilibrium with 17. The formation of 3d from 10, phenyl glyoxal and morpholine must be occurring through 17 and the morpholine analogue of 16 as intermediates. Reaction of 17 with excess *N,N*-dimethylhydrazine, followed by oxidation would account for the formation of 6 as a byproduct in the reaction of 1a with this hydrazine.

The mechanism proposed (Chart 1) would predict that the presence of an excess of a new amine during the reaction of 1a with *N,N*-disubstituted-hydrazine to form 16 would lead to incorporation of the amine in 17 and hence into the final products 3. We were pleased to find that the reaction of 1a with 3 molar equivalents of *N,N*-dimethylhydrazine and 10 molar equivalents of

morpholine indeed gave a mixture of 3a and 3d approximately in the ratio of 3 : 10 (^1H nmr). Pure 3d was isolated from this mixture in 55% yield and identified. When excess morpholine was replaced by *N,N*-dibenzylamine or aniline, 3f and 3j were isolable although yields were unsatisfactory (12% and 6%). Excess *n*-propylamine led to double incorporation, both at positions 1 and 3 to give 4 in 30% yield along with a little 3a. Its formation can be rationalised by assuming that 17 not only adds *n*-propylamine but also suffers an exchange of the imino group with the primary amine to give an analogue of 16 carrying two *n*-propyl groups.

Lastly, we studied the action of *N*-aminopiperidine with α -dimedonylpropiophenone (18). The reaction was sluggish and gave a complex mixture of products from which 9b and 23 were obtained in 12% and 4% yield respectively. The structure of 9b rested on analytical and spectral data. Identity was further established by comparison with a sample obtained by fusing 18 with ammonium carbonate. The structure of 23 was deduced from analytical as well as ir, nmr and mass spectral data. The ^1H nmr spectrum was particularly diagnostic, showing the indole α -H as a singlet at δ 7.60 ppm. Signals were lacking for both NH and β -protons. We propose the tentative mechanism shown in Chart 2.

Chart 2

In the reaction of 18 with *N*-aminopiperidine, species 19 analogous to 17 is formed initially, but in the presence of excess of the reagent, 19 is transformed into 20. The dieneamine tautomer 21 of 20 can undergo intramolecular addition to form 22. The observed final product 23 could arise by the oxidation of 22 by species 19 which in turn gets reduced to 24 leading to 9b by cyclodehydration.

Physical and spectral data of compounds are given in Tables 1 and 2.

Experimental

3-Amino-1,5,6,7-tetrahydro-4H-indol-4-ones (3).
Method A: A mixture of the ketone (1a; 10 mmol) with *N,N*-disubstituted-hydrazine (30 mmol) produced an exothermic reaction. After it subsided,

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF OTHER COMPOUNDS†

Compd. no.	Yield* %	M.p.** °C	Mol. formula (Mol. weight)	$\nu_{\max}$ (nujol) cm^{-1}	δ †
4	30 ^b	101–03 ^d	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_2\text{O}$ (338.5)	3 330, 1 630	ν 0.7 (6H, t, $2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2$), 6.13 (6H, s, 2OH, at C-6), 1.28 (4H, sex, $2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2$), 2.30 (s, C-5H ₂), 2.60 (s, C-7H ₂), 2.60 (2H, t, NHCH_2), 3.60 (2H, t, NOCH_2), 7.35 (s, 5ArH)
2a	31 ^a	Liquid	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_2\text{O}$ (338.5)	1 670	ν 1.30–2.00 (6H m, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2$), 2.00–2.60 (6H, m, $\text{COCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2$), 2.60–3.00 (4H, m, CH_2NCH_2), 6.30 (s, C-3H), 7.00–7.77 (m, 5ArH)
8	14 ^a	128–30 ^k	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2\text{O}$ (282.4)	1 620	ν 1.25–2.00 (6H, m, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2$), 2.20 (3H, s, 2-CH ₃), 2.50 (3H, s, COCH_3), 2.90–3.40 (4H, m, CH_2NOCH_2), 5.88 (s, C-4H), 7.10–7.50 (m, 3ArH), 7.50–7.90 (m, 2ArH)
9b	12 ^a	245–47 ^d	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{19}\text{NO}$ (258.3)	3 120, 1 620	ν 1.01 (6H, s, 2OH), 2.22 (2H, s, C-5H ₂), 2.68 (2H, s, C-7H ₂), 7.20–7.70 (m, 5ArH), 11.20 (br s, NH)
23	4 ^a	209–11 ^l	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$ (350.4)	1 670, 1 640	ν 1.07 (6H, s, 2CH ₃), 1.30–2.00 (6H, m, $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2$), 2.23 (2H, s, C-5H ₂), 2.73 (2H, s, C-7H ₂), 2.85–3.20 (4H, m, CH_2NOCH_2), 7.20–8.00 (m, 5ArH), 7.60 (s, C-2H)

Explanation of symbols †, *, **, † same as in Table 1.

the mixture was treated with ethanol (5 ml) and refluxed for 15 min. It was then cooled and the resulting solid was washed with ethanol and recrystallised (3; Table 1). 3d formed an oxime, m.p. 285°d (acetone-ethanol), $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{25}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$. In case of *N*-methylpiperazine, the product did not crystallise out from the reaction. It was obtained by removal of ethanol and trituration of the residue with water. In case of *N,N*-dibenzylhydrazine, there was very little initial exothermic reaction. The mixture was diluted with ethanol (25 ml) and refluxed for 4 h and allowed to cool to 28°. After 1 h, the product was filtered and recrystallised to give 3f. Further crops were obtained from the mother liquor by concentration. In the case of 3a, the mother liquor of crystallisation from a 20 mmol batch was evaporated and the residue chromatographed on a column of silica gel (70 g) in benzene-chloroform (1:3). The same mixture was used as eluent and 50 ml fractions collected. From fractions 1–3, methylene bis-dimedone (5; 0.2 g) was obtained, m.p. and m.m.p. 188–91°, $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_4$. Fractions 7–21 gave the yellow bis-hydrazone (8), m.p. 160–61° (aqueous ethanol); $\nu_{\max}$ (nujol) 1 655 and 1 600 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 1.00 (6H, s, 2CH₃), 2.18 (2H, s, CH₂), 2.50 (2H, s, CH₂), 2.50 (6H, s, 2N-CH₃), 2.55 (6H, s, 2N-CH₃), 7.10–7.45 (m, 3 ArH), 7.45–7.80 (m, 2 ArH) and 13.50 (br s, NH); $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2$, M^+ at m/z 356.

From the reaction of 1d with *N*-aminopiperidine, 3k crystallised out. The mother liquor was evaporated and the residue chromatographed over silica gel, elution being done with benzene-chloroform (1:3). The first fractions were combined and evaporated to give 2a as an oil.

Method B: A mixture of the ketone (1a; 10 mmol), *N,N*-dimethylhydrazine (30 mmol) and the appropriate amine (100 mmol; morpholine, dibenzylamine, aniline or *n*-propylamine) in ethanol (15

ml) was refluxed for 3 h. The solution was then diluted with water. In the case of morpholine, a crystalline product was obtained which was recrystallised from acetone-ethanol to give 3d. In the case of aniline, the product was obtained as an oil by extraction with ether and subsequently recrystallised to give 3j. In the case of dibenzylamine, the initial crystalline product corresponded to 3a. The mother liquors were worked up and fractionally crystallised from ether to give 3f. In the case of *n*-propylamine, the gummy product was treated with dilute HCl to give a small amount of the insoluble HCl salt of 3a. The acid-soluble part was basified and extracted with ether to give 4.

Reaction of 18 with *N*-aminopiperidine: A mixture of 18 (2.15 g, 8 mmol) and *N*-aminopiperidine (2.4 g, 24 mmol) (no exothermic reaction) was heated at 100° for 1.5 h. The gummy product was then washed with water and subjected to chromatography over silica gel in benzene-chloroform (2:1). The same solvent mixture was used for elution and approximately 50 ml fractions were collected. Fractions 3–11 were combined and evaporated. The residue became crystalline with ethanol and was recrystallised from the same solvent to give 9b, m.p. and m.m.p. with an authentic specimen, 245–47°, $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{19}\text{NO}$. Fraction 3l was evaporated and the residue crystallised from acetone-methanol to give 23, m.p. 209–11°, $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$; M^+ at m/z 350.

Reaction of 7 with *N*-aminopiperidine: A mixture of 7 (2.8 g, 13 mmol) and *N*-aminopiperidine (2.2 g, 26 mmol) in ethanol (10 ml) was refluxed for 2 h. The solvent was then removed and the residue rubbed with methanol to give 8.

2-Phenyl-3-amino-6,6-dimethyl-1,5,6,7-tetrahydro-4H-indol-4-one (3i): A solution of 3f (1 g) in ethanol (25 ml) was shaken with hydrogen at 1 atm

pressure and 29° in the presence of 10% Pd-C catalyst (0.3 g) for 10 h. The mixture was then filtered and the filtrate evaporated. The residue was triturated with hexane to give 3i which was recrystallised.

Deamination of 3i : 3i (0.1 g) was dissolved in 2N sulphuric acid (6 ml) by warming. The resulting clear solution was rapidly cooled and at 0° treated with sodium nitrite (50 mg) in water (0.1 ml). The diazonium sulphate separated immediately as white crystals which were suspended in ethanol (5 ml) and refluxed for 1 h. The solution was concentrated to give 9a as gummy crystals. The product was purified by filtration through a small column of silica gel in chloroform and recrystallised from ethanol (20 mg), m.p. and m.m.p. with authentic sample, 235-36°; C₁₆H₁₇NO.

Formation of 3d from aminoketone (10), phenyl glyoxal and morpholine : A mixture of aminoketone (10; 2.8 g, 20 mmol), phenyl glyoxal hydrate (3.0

g, 20 mmol) and morpholine (1.7 g, 20 mmol) in ethanol (40 ml) was refluxed for 2 h. The solvent was then removed and the residual gum, after washing with water, separated into dilute HCl soluble and insoluble fractions. The acidic extract was made alkaline with aqueous sodium hydroxide to give gummy crystals, which were separated and rubbed with ethanol to give 3d (0.4 g), m.p. and m.m.p. 295-97°.

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